
Research on the Creative Design of Freehand Zentangle Art

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Abstract The objects of this article are Department of Visual Communication Design students, who made point, line, and plane compositions on unlimited subjects using the creative technique of freehand Zentangle art. They also carried out industry-academia cooperation with manufacturers in the visual design of leather carving products. As a result, the teachers and students were able to generate creative concepts and design visual diagrams according to practical issues in the teaching and learning of the professional design course and achieve the curriculum goal of combining theory and practice.

Keywords Freehand Creation, Leather Carving Products, Zentangle, Visual Design

Introduction

This article signed an industry-academia cooperation with Changpeng Handicraft Workshop and integrated it in the works made in the design professional course. Students were allowed to carry out visual design according to the point, line, and plane concept using the method of freehand Zentangle art. Excellent works were selected according to the evaluation mechanism and provided to manufacturers as their reference for the development of a visual map for the development of leather carving products.

This research topic allows students to integrate theoretical knowledge into practice through industry-academia cooperation, thus achieving practical skills training and ability improvement. It can also help students understand the industry's demand for design manpower and the actual situation of industrial product development at an early stage.

The Creative Idea

Some scholars use Zentangle art technique as a way for the subjects to relieve stress. Some studies point out that the seemingly abstract art creation has its own rules. Assuredly, visual design is very important in the overall creation of the artwork [4].

Visual design is associated with the use of some basic design elements and principles. Those are applied by the designers in the various disciplines for aesthetic purposes, relying on an intuitive and subjective process [1]. Zentangle art relaxes the body and mind through the process of concentrating while painting, achieving a healing effect [3]. We show how the decisions made by artists to use specific design conventions were not random but instead were deeply implicated in, and shaped by, social processes acquired through learning or enculturation [2].

Creative Skills

The composition of point, line, and plane is one of the most basic courses for learning visual communication design. Learners must be trained and learn these skills whether in freehand or digital drawing in order to meet the future needs of the design market.

Secondly, Zentangle art can be one of the works for the creative skills of point, line, and plane, especially for beginners. It is easier to learn. Teachers explain through actual cases and provide students with creative thinking through imitation and modeling of object shapes. Hence, theoretical knowledge can be integrated into practical freehand exercises to strengthen the students' practical ability.

Achievements Exhibition

The teacher and industry practitioner jointly formulated: (1) visual elements (30%); (2) creative expression (30%); (3) color scheme (30%); (4) design concept (10%) evaluation criteria, to provide a reference for the industry in their development of innovative products (figure 1).

Figure 1: Design results

Results and Contributions

Teachers are still enthusiastic about education, despite the severe external pressure of declining birthrates. They try their best to use the best teaching materials and teaching methods to give students a diverse, lively, and

practical learning experience, so as to achieve the developmental goal of emphasizing the combination of theory and practice in design education.

Furthermore, if teachers can integrate the necessary theoretical knowledge into the process of teaching and learning, as well as add practical topics from the industry to allow students to practice, they can better achieve the educational goals of the design professional courses and help students improve their professional abilities.

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